

A New Leucoanthocyanin from the Stem of *Diospyros-peregrina*

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The phytochemical examination of the stem of *Diospyros-peregrina* resulted in the isolation of β -sitosterol and a new leucoanthocyanin which was characterized as Leuco-pelargonidin-3- α -L-rhamnopyranoside.

DIOSPYROS-PEREGRINA (N. O. Ebenaceae) is reputed for its medicinal properties^{1,2}. The plant was selected for chemical examination because a review of the available literature revealed that very little work has been done only on the bark of this plant.

Results and Discussion

A compound m.p. 136-7° was isolated from the petroleum ether extract of water insoluble fraction of the stem. It was identified as β -sitosterol by the colour reactions, m.p., m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol.

The ethyl acetate extract of the water soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract of the stem afforded a Leucoanthocyanin m.p. 89-90°. Hydrolysis of the glycoside with hydrochloric acid yielded an orange-red coloured anthocyanidin and a sugar which was characterized as rhamnose by co-chromatography with an authentic sample and osazone formation. The orange-red coloured anthocyanidin was identified as pelargonidin³ by the usual tests and confirmed by co-chromatography with an authentic sample of pelargonidin obtained from orange-red *Dahlia* flowers.

Periodate oxidation of the glycoside showed the consumption of 2.1 moles of periodate with the production of 1.01 moles of formic acid per mole of the glycoside suggesting the presence of one unit of sugar in pyranose form.

The linkage of sugar with the aglycone was determined by polymerisation, periodate oxidation and colour reactions as follows :

When refluxed with mineral acids glycoside polymerised, indicating that there is a free hydroxyl group at position-4*.

Formation of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid on oxidation with neutral potassium permanganate showed that there is a free hydroxyl group at position-4'.

The glycoside spotted on a filter paper produced a red colour on being sprayed with *p*-toluene sulphonic acid and subsequent heating. This test is specific for a free hydroxyl group at position-5^{4,6}.

A positive colour with vanillin-hydrochloric acid reagent indicated the presence of phloroglucinol unit in the molecule, i.e., free hydroxyl groups at position 5 and 7.

Thus the only position left for the linkage of sugar moiety is 3.

The possibility of the sugar moiety being linked at position 5 or 7 was also ruled out by the study of periodate oxidation, when the glycoside consumed 2.1 moles of periodate with liberation of 1.01 moles of formic acid. Had the sugar moiety been linked at the position 5 or 7 the compound would have consumed 3 moles of periodate instead of 2.1 (two for the sugar and one for the hydroxyl groups in position 3 and 4).

Failure of the glycoside to undergo emulsin hydrolysis showed the presence of an α -linkage between the sugar and the aglycone.

On the basis of studies made, the glycoside has been assigned the following structure :

Experimental

Plant Material :

The plant material was locally collected and was identified by the Botanical Survey of India, Allahabad.

Isolation and Purification

The air dried powdered stem (2 kg) was refluxed with hot ethanol on a steam bath. The total ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the concentrate was poured into a large excess of distilled water with continuous stirring. The water insoluble portion was extracted with petroleum ether and the petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over neutral Alumina. Elution with petroleum ether-Benzene (1 : 1, v/v) gave a compound which was identified as β -sitosterol by usual tests. The water soluble fraction was subjected to liquid-liquid extraction using petroleum ether, benzene and ethyl acetate separately. The ethyl acetate fraction was concentrated and to it was added excess of pet. ether. A buff-coloured compound was precipitated. It was dissolved in ethyl acetate and reprecipitated with pet. ether. The process was repeated till a pure white compound m.p. 89-90° was obtained. It gave a single spot on paper chromatography (Acetic Acid : Conc. HCl : Water 5 : 1 : 5 (v/v), $R_f=0.63$) and T.L.C. plate (*n*-Butanol : Acetic Acid : Water 5 : 1 : 5 (v/v), $R_f=0.72$).

It gave an orange red colour on treatment with ethanolic hydrochloric acid, dull brown colour with ferric chloride, deep pink colour with vanillin-hydrochloric acid reagent and a positive Molisch test. (Found C, 57.92% ; H, 5.41% ; $C_{21}H_{24}O_{10}$ requires C, 57.19% ; H, 5.5%).

The i.r. spectrum of the glycoside (in KBr phase) showed the following main peaks.

830 cm^{-1} , 1050 cm^{-1} , 1235 cm^{-1} , 1440 cm^{-1} , 1510 cm^{-1} , 1610 cm^{-1} , 3100 cm^{-1} .

Study of the Glycoside :

Hydrolysis :

The glycoside (0.02 g) was refluxed with 5% ethanolic hydrochloric acid (10 ml) for 2 hr. One of the products of hydrolysis was identified as pelargonidin by the study of its visible spectra (0.1% ethanolic-HCl, λ_{max} -528 nm, Lit, λ_{max} -530 nm ; no bathochromic shift in λ_{max} with $AlCl_3$), R_f value (Paper chromatography, solvent-Acetic Acid : Conc. HCl : Water 5 : 1 : 5 (v/v), $R_f=0.54$, Lit. $R_f=0.55$) and specific colour reactions. The other product, a sugar was identified as L-Rhamnose (Paper chromatography, solvent, *n*-Butanol : Acetic Acid : Water 4 : 1 : 5 (v/v), spray A.H.P. ; $R_f=0.36$; authentic rhamnose $R_f=0.38$; Osazone m.p.=189° (Lit. m.p.=191°).

Acetylation and Acetyl Percentage Determination :

The glycoside (0.03 g) was acetylated using acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (5 ml) at room temperature. The acetylated product was poured over crushed ice and left overnight. The white compound thus obtained was filtered, dried and purified from methanol. It melted at 70°. The percentage of the acetyl groups in the acetylated product was determined by the method of Wisenberger⁷ as described by Belcher and Godbert⁸. Found : $COCH_3$, 40.92% ; $C_{21}H_{17}O_{10}(COCH_3)_7$ requires ; $-COCH_3$, 41.23%.

Methylation :

The glycoside (0.05 g) was refluxed with Dimethyl Sulphate (0.5 ml) and potassium carbonate (1 g) in dry acetone (30 ml) for 8 hr. After cooling the potassium salt was filtered off and washed with acetone. The combined filtrate and washings were concentrated and poured over crushed ice and allowed to stand overnight. The solid so obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and purified from methanol ; m.p. 80°.

Potassium Permanganate Oxidation :

The glycoside (0.05 g) was dissolved in acetone (30 ml) and potassium permanganate (1 g) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hours. After cooling the reaction mixture, manganese dioxide was dissolved by adding sodium bisulphite. The solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was shaken with saturated solution of aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The aqueous layer after acidification was again extracted with ether. The compound obtained from this was identified as *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid m.p. 212°. (Lit. 214°).

Enzymatic Hydrolysis :

Emulsin prepared from almonds⁹ was added to the glycoside solution. The glycoside remained unaffected showing an α -linkage between the sugar and the aglycone.

Periodate Oxidation :

The glycoside (0.02 g) dissolved in 25 ml of ethanol was treated with 25 ml of 0.1M solution of sodium metaperiodate. The periodate consumed and formic acid liberated were titrated by the titrimetric method of Jones *et al*¹⁰. Moles of periodate consumed = 2.1. Moles of formic acid liberated = 1.01.

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